

DEVELOPMENT OF PARALLEL FINITE ELEMENT METHOD SOFTWARE FOR ANALYZING PROGRESSIVE INTERFACE FAILURE OF LARGE-SCALE CFRP MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites (CFRP) exhibit highly complex failure mechanisms because they include fiber–matrix and interlaminar interfaces. Detailed modeling of fibers, matrices, and interfaces for conducting accurate progressive-damage analysis of CFRP requires large-scale finite-element meshes. We develop parallel finite element analysis (FEA) software, that can simulate failure of large-scale CFRP models including interfaces. An open-source large-scale parallel FEA program FrontISTR is used as a seed program, and a cohesive element is implemented to model the interfaces. First, we verified this software by comparing it with commercial software using a small-scale model. Second, we validated the software by simulating double cantilever beam (DCB) experiments to measure the interlaminar strength. We evaluate the mesh size effects onto interfacial-damage analysis of DCB experiments by using the software. Five simulation scales are conducted with varying element sizes. As the mesh size decreases, the simulation results show that the maximum load converges to a certain value. The load agrees well with the experimental value. We found that the software can analyze progressive damage of large-scale models with more than 77 million degrees of freedom by using 4,096 cores.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites (CFRP) are currently used for aircraft applications because of their excellent specific strength and specific elasticity. However, CFRPs exhibit highly complex interactive failure mechanisms because they include fiber–matrix interfaces and interlaminar interfaces, as shown in Fig. 1. It is necessary to model all these damages to accurately predict the damage of CFRP laminates. However, problems occur with large-scale models. To address this, in recent years, finite element method software capable of large-scale structural analysis has been developed along with the improvement in computer performance. One such large-scale parallel finite element analysis software is FrontISTR [1]. It can analyze large-scale problems by parallel computation based on domain decomposition. It can be used in systems ranging from personal computers to supercomputers. It was developed in a national project in Japan, and is under continuous development and maintenance. Large-scale analysis cases with hundreds of millions of degrees of freedom using FrontISTR have been reported thus far [2, 3]. In addition, since it is open source and released as an MIT license, customization, such as adding new functions according to needs, can be performed without cost.

In this study, we develop finite element software that can analyze large-scale models of CFRP that model all damage in detail by using FrontISTR as a seed program. We focus on the analysis of damage propagation at the interface, which is characteristic of composite materials. We implement a cohesive element that can model interface damage. This element is used for damage-propagation analysis of laminated interfaces [4–6]. It can also be used for damage-development analysis between the fiber and matrix [7–9] in the simulation of microbond tests [10]. First, we verified this software by comparing it with commercial software using a small-scale model. Next, we validate the software by comparing

experiment results. We conduct a simulation for the double cantilever beam (DCB) test, which is used to determine the mode I fracture toughness value of the laminated interface. Damage-progression analysis has been known to be affected by mesh size. The influence of mesh size is evaluated in the simulation of a DCB test using a two-dimensional model [5]. In this study, we change the mesh size from a small-scale to a large-scale model (up to 76.5 million degrees of freedom) in three dimensions, and evaluate the effect of mesh size on maximum load.

Figure 1: Failure of CFRP.

2 FORMULATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERFACE-DAMAGE MODEL

2.1 Cohesive element

We use cohesive elements to model interface damage in CFRP. The formulation of the cohesive element [4] implemented into FrontISTR in this research is shown as follows. The topology of the cohesive element is shown in Fig. 2. The node numbers in the figure refer to the local node numbers in the element. The strain is determined from the relative distance between the lower surface consisting of nodes 1, 2, 3, and 4, and the upper surface consisting of nodes 5, 6, 7, and 8. We model the interface with zero initial thickness because the adhesive layer has a small thickness. The strain and the separation distance (displacement) of the interface have a same value by setting the layer thickness to one. The B-matrix (strain-displacement relationship) \mathbf{B} is defined as follows.

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} -N_1 & 0 & 0 & -N_2 & 0 & 0 & -N_3 & 0 & 0 & -N_4 & 0 & 0 & N_1 & 0 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & 0 & N_4 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -N_1 & 0 & 0 & -N_2 & 0 & 0 & -N_3 & 0 & 0 & -N_4 & 0 & 0 & N_1 & 0 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & 0 & N_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -N_1 & 0 & 0 & -N_2 & 0 & 0 & -N_3 & 0 & 0 & -N_4 & 0 & 0 & N_1 & 0 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & 0 & N_4 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Here, N_1 , N_2 , N_3 , and N_4 are shape functions of two-dimensional isoparametric elements. In the cohesive element, the orientation of the interface on the model is important, and thus, the compressive tension and shear directions of the interface are expressed in the local coordinate system. The displacement vector of the interface in the local coordinate system $\boldsymbol{\delta}'$ is obtained as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\delta}' &= \mathbf{B}\mathbf{P}\mathbf{u} \\ &= \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}' \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where $\boldsymbol{\delta}'$ has three components, namely one displacement in the tension and compression direction and two displacements in the shear direction. We define the nodal displacement vector of the global coordinate system as \mathbf{u} , the nodal displacement vector of the local coordinate system as \mathbf{u}' , and the coordinate transformation matrix from the global to the local coordinate system as \mathbf{P} .

We use the interface construction law based on continuum damage mechanics. The stress in each direction can be obtained from Equations (3), (4), and (5).

$$\sigma'_n = \begin{cases} (1 - \varphi)K'_n\delta'_n & \delta'_n \geq 0 \\ K'_n\delta'_n & \delta'_n < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma'_s = (1 - \varphi)K'_s\delta'_s \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma'_t = (1 - \varphi)K'_t\delta'_t \quad (5)$$

We define the damage variable as φ . We set the stress, stiffness, and displacement in the tensile and compressive direction as σ'_n , K'_n , and δ'_n , respectively; and the stress, stiffness, and displacement in the two shear directions as σ'_s , σ'_t , K'_s , K'_t , δ'_s , and δ'_t , respectively. The stress-strain matrix in the local coordinate system \mathbf{D}' after damage is as shown in equation (6).

$$\mathbf{D}' = \begin{cases} \begin{pmatrix} (1 - \varphi)K'_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (1 - \varphi)K'_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1 - \varphi)K'_t \end{pmatrix} & \delta'_n \geq 0 \\ \begin{pmatrix} K'_n & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (1 - \varphi)K'_s & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1 - \varphi)K'_t \end{pmatrix} & \delta'_n < 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The damage variable φ changes from 0 to 1, where $\varphi = 0$ indicates no damage, and $\varphi = 1$ indicates destruction. Damage occurs when equation (7) holds.

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle \delta'_n \rangle}{\delta_n^o} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\delta'_s}{\delta_s^o} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\delta'_t}{\delta_t^o} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

We define the displacement when damage occurs in the tensile and two shear directions as $\delta_n^o, \delta_s^o, \delta_t^o$ respectively. The symbol $\langle \rangle$ represents the Macaulay bracket. Here, the effective displacement δ_m is determined by equation (8).

$$\delta_m = \sqrt{\langle \delta'_n \rangle^2 + \delta_s'^2 + \delta_t'^2} \quad (8)$$

The evolution rule of the damage variable φ can be obtained from equation (9).

$$\varphi = \frac{\delta_m^f (\delta_m^{max} - \delta_m^o)}{\delta_m^{max} (\delta_m^f - \delta_m^o)} \quad (9)$$

The effective displacement at the onset of damage is δ_m^o , the effective displacement at failure is δ_m^f , and the maximum effective displacement at load history is δ_m^{max} . These relationships can be illustrated as shown in Fig. 3 if the characteristics do not differ in each direction. K is the stiffness of the interface, T is the interface strength, and the area of the triangle is the fracture toughness value G . In this case, we can parameterize the fracture properties of the interface with three values, for example, K , T , and G . Since analysis using cohesive elements has nonlinearity of damage development, we perform incremental analysis with the Newton-Raphson method. The element tangent stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_e is obtained from equations (10), and the increment of the internal force vector of the element $\Delta \mathbf{Q}_e$ is obtained from equation (11).

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \int_s \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{P}^T \mathbf{D}' \mathbf{P} \mathbf{B} ds \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{Q}_e = \int_s \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \Delta \mathbf{u} ds \quad (11)$$

The stress-strain matrix in the global coordinate system is \mathbf{D} , the area of the adhesive element is s , and the incremental value of the nodal displacement vector in the global coordinate system is $\Delta \mathbf{u}$. Newton-Cotes numerical integration is used for these integrations.

Figure 2: Topology of cohesive element.

Figure 3: Interface properties.

2.2 Accuracy verification of cohesive elements

2.2.1 Methods of verification

We compare the results of FrontISTR with those of the commercial generic finite element software Abaqus to verify the accuracy of FrontISTR implemented with the cohesive element. The model for verification is shown in Fig. 4. Cohesive elements are placed on the sides of the cylinder, which is divided into quarters so that it can be applied to fiber-resin interfaces as well as laminated interfaces. We completely fix the top of the model, and give the end face of the cylinder a forced displacement (x-direction 0.5 mm, y-direction 0.5 mm, z-direction 0.5 mm). The arrows in Fig. 4 indicate forced displacement. Table 1 shows the interface material properties of the cohesive elements. Elements other than cohesive elements are divided into hexahedral primary elements. The Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of these elements is 200 GPa and 0.3, respectively. These analysis conditions are common to FrontISTR and Abaqus. To examine the parallel computing performance based on domain division, we perform both serial and parallel computing in the analysis using FrontISTR. The model is divided into two, four, and eight subdomains. Figure 5 shows an example of decomposition into eight subdomains, including the cohesive element as an example of domain decomposition.

Figure 4: Evaluation model for cohesive elements.

Table 1: Interface material properties for evaluation model.

K'_n	K'_s	K'_t	
1000 N/mm ³	100 N/mm ³	10 N/mm ³	
δ_n^o	δ_s^o	δ_t^o	δ_m^f
0.5 mm	0.3 mm	0.4 mm	0.5 mm

Figure 5: Domain decomposition of evaluation model.

2.2.2 Results of verification

We chose two elements from the cohesive elements and compared the displacement, stress, and damage variables at the same integration point. Figure 6 shows the position of the cohesive elements used for comparison. Table 2 shows the comparison in element 4122, and Table 3 shows the comparison in element 4051 where the damage is further advanced. The color of the contour plot represents the value of the damage variable. The difference in the tables is the difference based on the Abaqus value. The results of FrontISTR and those of Abaqus agree with good accuracy. Table 4 shows the comparison results of serial and parallel calculations in element 4051. Parallel computing does not affect the analysis results. We confirmed that FrontISTR can perform interface-damage progress analysis with the same calculation accuracy as proven software, even in parallel calculation by domain decomposition.

Figure 6: Color depicts values of φ for comparison.

Table 2: Comparison set of element 4122.

	FrontISTR	Abaqus	Difference [%]
δ'_n [mm]	0.6658	0.6655	0.05
δ'_s [mm]	0.02591	0.02534	2.25
δ'_t [mm]	0.5222	0.5230	0.15
σ'_n [MPa]	76.25	75.98	0.17
σ'_s [MPa]	0.2967	0.2897	0.37
σ'_t [MPa]	0.5981	0.5971	2.42
Damage	0.8855	0.8858	0.03

Table 3: Comparison set of element 4051.

	FrontISTR	Abaqus	Difference [%]
δ'_n [mm]	0.5221	0.5221	0.00
δ'_s [mm]	0.4754	0.4754	0.00
δ'_t [mm]	0.4997	0.5003	0.12
σ'_n [MPa]	7.203	7.042	2.27
σ'_s [MPa]	0.6559	0.6413	2.28
σ'_t [MPa]	0.06893	0.06749	2.13
Damage	0.9862	0.9865	0.03

Table 4: Comparison set of serial and parallel analyses.

	Serial	2 MPI	4 MPI	8 MPI
δ'_n [mm]	0.5221	0.5221	0.5221	0.5221
δ'_s [mm]	0.4754	0.4754	0.4754	0.4754
δ'_t [mm]	0.4997	0.4997	0.4997	0.4997
σ'_n [MPa]	7.203	7.203	7.203	7.203
σ'_s [MPa]	0.6559	0.6559	0.6559	0.6559
σ'_t [MPa]	0.06893	0.06893	0.06893	0.06893
Damage	0.9862	0.9862	0.9862	0.9862

3 VALIDATION OF THE SOFTWARE BY SIMULATING DCB TEST

3.1 Methods

We performed simulations of the DCB test shown in Fig. 7 using the developed software. The calculation model is a half-symmetric model. Two CFRP unidirectional plies, each with a thickness of 1.98 mm, are stacked. The initial crack is 55 mm, and a cohesive element is placed from the tip of the crack to the end of the specimen to model the interface. The parts other than the interface are divided into hexahedral primary elements. Table 5 [5] shows the orthotropic elastic properties of CFRP. Subscripts 1, 2, and 3 indicate the three orthogonal axes. Axis 1 is the fiber direction. E, G, and ν are the elastic modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio, respectively. The interface material properties are shown in Table 6 [5]. G_{IC} , K, and T are the fracture toughness value in mode I, interface stiffness, and interface strength in the tensile direction, respectively. In this simulation, the fracture toughness value, interface stiffness, and interface strength in the shear direction are set to the same values as those in the tensile direction.

We simulate with mesh sizes of 1, 0.5, 0.25, 0.125, and 0.0625 mm. The mesh shape is a rectangular solid. The length of the longitudinal side is set as the mesh size. The mesh size is denoted as h . Forced positive and negative displacement in the z-direction can be applied to the top and bottom of the end face where the initial crack is located. A half-symmetric model is used considering the symmetry of the model. We consider the value obtained by doubling the total value of the reaction force acting on the

node given the forced displacement as the load in the DCB test. The Newton-Raphson iterative calculation is used for geometrical nonlinearity and damage nonlinearity. The interface damage progression analysis is carried out until the load decreases. The effect of mesh size on maximum load is evaluated. In addition, in the case of $h = 0.125$ mm, analysis to open crack displacement up to 16 mm and unload is conducted.

The supercomputer system Oakforest-PACS is employed. It consists of 8,208 nodes, and one node consists of 68 cores of CPU and a total of 112 GB of memory. In FrontISTR, MPI parallel calculation by subdomains and thread parallel calculation by OpenMP can be used as parallel computing. Table 7 shows the number of elements, number of nodes, degree of freedom (DOF), number of MPI and OpenMP in parallel, and number of nodes of Oakforest-PACS used for each condition. The domain decomposition is not performed for the model of $h = 1$ mm. We use the CG method for the linear solver and use an AMG preconditioner.

Figure 7: DCB model.

Table 5: Mechanical properties for DCB simulation [5].

E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$G_{12}=G_{13}$
150.0 GPa	11.0 GPa	6.0 GPa
G_{23}	$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	ν_{23}
3.7 GPa	0.25	0.45

Table 6: Interface material properties for DCB simulation [5].

G_{IC}	K	T
0.352 N/mm	10^6 N/mm ³	60 MPa

Table 7: Calculation conditions.

Mesh size [mm]	1	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625
Number of elements	6.95×10^3	5.18×10^4	3.99×10^5	3.13×10^6	2.48×10^7
Number of nodes	9.97×10^3	6.32×10^4	4.44×10^5	3.31×10^6	2.55×10^7
DOF	2.99×10^4	1.90×10^5	1.33×10^6	9.92×10^6	7.65×10^7
MPI	-	8	64	512	512
OpenMP	8	8	8	8	8
Node of Oakforest-PACS	1	1	8	64	64

3.2 Results and discussion

The relationship between h and the maximum load is shown in Fig.8. The maximum load converges as the mesh size decreases. The maximum load at $h = 0.0625$ mm is 62.6 N and the experimental value [4] is 62.5 N. It is found that the simulation result agrees well with that of the experiment as the mesh size decreases. The distribution of tractions ahead of the crack tip at COD=3.6 mm is shown in Fig.9. The distribution of damage variables at a COD of 5.2 mm is shown in Fig. 10. The traction distribution and damage distribution at $h = 0.125$ mm are similar to those at $h = 0.0625$ mm.

Fig.8 Effect of mesh size on maximum load.

Fig.9 Distribution of tractions ahead of the crack tip at COD=3.6 mm.

Fig.10 Distribution of damage ahead of the crack tip at COD=5.2 mm.

The damage variable contour plot of the $h = 0.125$ mm model at a COD of 16 mm is shown in Fig. 11. The load-COD curves at $h = 0.125$ mm and experiments are shown in Fig.12. The simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental results.

The calculation time and the number of iterations of Newton-Raphson for each mesh size are shown in Table 8. The time until the CG method converges in the first iteration of the Newton-Raphson method for a large-scale model ($h = 0.0625$ mm) with 76.5 million degrees of freedom is 27.9 seconds using parallel computation by the domain decomposition.

Fig.11 Damage variable contour of the $h = 0.125$ mm model at a COD of 16 mm.

Fig.12 Load-COD curves.

Table 8: Calculation time and the number of iterations of Newton-Raphson.

Mesh size	1	0.5	0.25	0.125	0.0625
First CG method calculation time [s]	0.94	1.21	1.51	2.94	27.9
Total Newton-Raphson iterations	132	235	234	391	401
Newton-Raphson iterations at the last substep	35	163	144	198	204
Total calculation time [s]	276	532	776	1,971	17,352

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we developed parallel finite element analysis software that can analyze interface-damage progression of large-scale CFRP models using cohesive elements. We verified the software by comparing it with commercial software using a small-scale model. In addition, we validated the software by simulating DCB tests, and evaluated the effects of mesh size on interlaminar damage-progression analysis. The results obtained in this study are as follows.

(1) We implemented a cohesive element in the open-source structural-analysis software FrontISTR, and developed a software that can perform damage evolution analysis by parallel computation based on domain decomposition. In the interface damage-progressive analysis, FrontISTR was able to obtain the same accuracy results as commercial software. It was also confirmed that the domain decomposition for parallel computing did not affect the analysis results.

(2) The DCB test was simulated using the developed software. For a sufficiently small mesh size, the maximum load converges, and the result agrees well with the experimental value [4]. The load-COD curve of the $h = 0.125\text{mm}$ model matched well with curves of the experiments [4].

(3) The developed software can analyze progressive damage of large-scale models with more than 77 million degrees of freedom by using 4,096 cores.

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